

Emmy-Noether FINAL REPORT

1 General Information

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Name of the applicant: Rettig, Laurenz
Office address: Fritz Haber Institute of the Max Planck Society, Department of Physical Chemistry, Faradayweg 4-6, 12159 Berlin
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2 Summary

English

Correlated materials are characterized by a variety of interactions between the elementary degrees of freedom, leading to novel ground states with broken symmetries and often intriguing properties. Goal of this project was to combine several ultrafast time-resolved techniques to quantify these interactions, and unravel their relevance in various complex quantum materials. Charge-Density wave (CDW) materials were chosen as model system for electron-phonon (e-ph) coupling. In the CDW material TbTe_3 , we quantified based on time-resolved photoemission and diffraction experiments the transient CDW energy surface, extracted the ultrafast CDW trajectories after a photoinduced phase transition, and demonstrated a transient CDW stabilization due to transiently suppressed lattice fluctuations. Furthermore, the CDW dependence of fundamental interactions such as e-ph and electron-electron coupling was studied on the level of individual bands and modes. In TaS_2 , coherent control of the transition into a metastable, hidden state was demonstrated.

Magnetic interactions and exchange coupling were studied in various antiferromagnetic (AFM) materials by time-resolved photoemission and time-resolved resonant x-ray diffraction. Based on a systematic study of magnetization dynamics in intermetallics of type LnRh_2Si_2 (Ln =rare earth atom), we uncovered a fundamental relation between angular momentum transfer between AFM sublattices, and interlayer exchange coupling, which also depends sensitively on the conduction electron properties. In addition, the energy flow between the different subsystems was systematically studied. In GdRh_2Si_2 , optical control of the direction of the AFM order as well as excitation of coherent magnons could be demonstrated, allowing us to quantify the magnetic-field dependent magnetic anisotropy energy.

Finally, the interaction between spin and lattice degrees of freedom in the Mott insulator NiO has been investigated by time-resolved electron diffraction, highlighting the relevance of exchange striction for a long-lasting nonthermal lattice state. In addition, charge order has been identified as dominant order parameter in the charge- and orbitally-ordered mixed-valence manganite $\text{Pr}_{0.5}\text{Ca}_{0.5}\text{MnO}_3$.

Overall, the project has shed light on the microscopic interactions driving complex phase transitions in various quantum materials, with promising results for applications e.g. in future information technology.

Deutsch

Korrelierte Materialien beherbergen eine Vielzahl von Wechselwirkungen zwischen den elementaren Freiheitsgraden, die zu neuartigen Grundzuständen mit gebrochener Symmetrie und oft verblüffenden Eigenschaften führen. Ziel dieses Projekts war die Kombination mehrerer ultraschneller zeitaufgelöster Techniken, um diese Wechselwirkungen zu quantifizieren und ihre Bedeutung in mehreren Klassen komplexer Quantenmaterialien zu entschlüsseln. Als Modellsystem für die Elektron-Phonon (e-ph)-Kopplung wurden Ladungsdichtewellen (CDW)-Materialien gewählt. Im CDW-Material TbTe_3 haben wir mittels zeitaufgelöster Photoemissions- und Beugungsexperimente die transiente CDW-Energiefläche quantifiziert, die ultraschnellen CDW-Trajektorien nach einem photoinduzierten Phasenübergang bestimmt, sowie eine transiente CDW-Stabilisierung aufgrund kurzzeitig unterdrückter Gitterfluktuation nachgewiesen. Darüber hinaus wurde die CDW-Abhängigkeit von fundamentalen Wechselwirkungen wie e-ph und Elektron-Elektron-Kopplung auf dem Niveau einzelner Bänder und Moden untersucht. In TaS_2 wurde die kohärente Kontrolle des Übergangs in einen metastabilen, verborgenen Zustand demonstriert.

Magnetische Wechselwirkungen und Austauschkopplung wurden in verschiedenen antiferromagnetischen (AFM) Materialien durch zeitaufgelöste Photoemission und zeitaufgelöste resonante Röntgenbeugung untersucht. Basierend auf einer systematischen Untersuchung der Magnetisierungsdynamik in intermetallischen Materialien des Typs LnRh_2Si_2 (Ln =Seltenerd-Atom) haben wir eine grundlegende Beziehung zwischen dem Drehimpulstransfer zwischen AFM-Untergittern und der Austauschkopplung zwischen den Ebenen aufgedeckt, die auch empfindlich von den Eigenschaften der Leitungselektronen abhängt. Darüber hinaus wurde der Energietransfer zwischen den verschiedenen Subsystemen systematisch untersucht. In GdRh_2Si_2 konnte die optische Kontrolle der Richtung der AFM-Spinordnung sowie die Anregung kohärenter Magnonen demonstriert werden, welche die Quantifizierung der magnetfeldabhängigen magnetischen Anisotropieenergie erlauben.

Schließlich demonstrierten Untersuchungen der Wechselwirkung zwischen Spin- und Gitterfreiheitsgraden im Mott-Isolator NiO mittels zeitaufgelöste Elektronenbeugung die Bedeutung magnetoelastischer Kopplung (exchange striction) für einen langlebigen nichtthermischen Gitterzustand. Darüber hinaus wurde die Ladungsordnung als dominanter Ordnungsparameter im ladungs- und orbital geordneten Manganit $\text{Pr}_{0.5}\text{Ca}_{0.5}\text{MnO}_3$ identifiziert.

Insgesamt hat das Projekt dazu beigetragen, die mikroskopischen Wechselwirkungen hinter komplexe Phasenübergänge in verschiedenen Quantenmaterialien zu erhellen, mit vielversprechenden Ergebnissen für Anwendungen z.B. in zukünftigen Informationstechnologien.

3 Scientific Progress Report

Background and objectives

The central goal of the Emmy-Noether project “*Beyond time constants: Quantifying interactions in correlated materials by complementary ultrafast time-domain approaches*” was the investigation of fundamental interactions in complex quantum materials and across phase transitions.

To this end, we employed complementary femtosecond time-resolved techniques, which allow direct access to the relevant fundamental degrees of freedom, i.e. the electronic, lattice, spin and orbital degrees of freedom (Fig. 1). A combination of time- and angle-resolved photoelectron spectroscopy (trARPES) and time-resolved diffraction methods (time-resolved X-ray and electron diffraction) were applied to different classes of correlated materials with specific broken-symmetry ground states.

The overarching goal of the project was, by combining such complementary approaches with suitable models and theories, to gain a deeper and quantitative description of the fundamental coupling parameters and energy landscapes that are the driving force for emerging order and broken-symmetry states.

The project was organized along three lines of research that each concentrate on a different kind of broken-symmetry state and associated interactions: one part investigated charge-density wave (CDW) order and associated phenomena rooting in strong electron-phonon (e-ph) coupling, while a second line of research was focused on antiferromagnetic (AFM) order and

Figure 1: Elementary degrees of freedom in correlated materials and their coupling channels. Time-resolved techniques sensitive to the respective degrees of freedom are indicated.

the coupling between the charge and spin system. Finally, a third part aimed at complex transition-metal oxides with various competing orders and multiple relevant energy scales.

Technical developments

Experimentally, a central part of the project relied on the investigation of the transient electronic structure by means of trARPES. Significant effort has been invested to further develop and advance this method, based on a unique high-repetition rate XUV trARPES setup [1]. This setup integrates both a conventional hemispherical analyzer and a novel time-of-flight momentum microscope [2], providing as a unique advantage the combination of two kinds of spectrometers into a single experimental setup. Part of this project and integral requirement for the project's research was a systematic comparison of the two spectrometers for time-resolved ARPES experiments including several different use cases [MDB20]. While intuitively, the momentum microscope due to its efficient and simultaneous collection of electrons with all in-plane momenta generally seems to be the superior instrument, our study shows that a number of restrictions apply in particular with the use of femtosecond laser pulses, which depending on the use case can make a hemispherical analyzer the more suitable choice. This complementarity of our two spectrometers has been elemental for a number of studies in this project. Furthermore, tools and frameworks were developed to handle the large and multidimensional datasets. In contrast to imaging-type detectors like CCD-camera-based hemispherical analyzers, the delay-line detector of the momentum microscope registers every single electron individually, which can be stored as a single-electron event-stream with multidimensional coordinates, e.g. $e^-(k_x, k_y, E_{kin}, t, T, p, \dots)$ with coordinates of in-plane momenta, kinetic energy, pump-probe delay, temperature, light polarization, etc. This approach allows for a flexible handling of the data after the experiment, and analysis in a multidimensional parameter space depending on the requirements of the study. As prerequisite and necessary building block for such an analysis pipeline, we developed a flexible, open-source framework for multidimensional binning of single-event data based on Python [XAA20].

Another central component of this project was the development and implementation of a pulsed laser deposition (PLD) setup for the growth of complex transition-metal films and heterostructures. While this project was initially delayed for various reasons, the system is operational now, and first results are presented below.

Charge-ordered systems

The first subproject focused on coupling phenomena of the electronic and the lattice system, predominantly charge density wave systems driven by e-ph coupling and Fermi surface (FS) nesting. Leading role in these studies had the PhD student Julian Maklar, supported by the

postdoc Jit Sarkar. Initially, the work focused on the quasi 2-dimensional (2D) CDW compound TbTe_3 [3]. CDW formation in this system is discussed to be driven by a combination of strongly directional e-ph coupling [4] and FS nesting, which leads to a unidirectional CDW where parts of the FS are gapped while others remain metallic. As has been shown previously by us and others, optical excitation suppresses the CDW gap and induces coherent amplitude mode oscillations of the order parameter [5–8]. However, a quantification of the coherent electronic and structural order parameters and transient CDW trajectories did not exist.

We studied the coherent CDW order parameter dynamics by a combination of XUV trARPES and time-resolved X-ray diffraction in a wide range of fluences, and extracted the coherent order parameter dynamics as well as the transient electronic temperature. While we observe a complete suppression of the CDW gap even for moderate fluences, the subsequent coherent oscillations of the CDW order parameter show a strong dependence on excitation density. Based on a time-dependent Ginzburg-Landau model, we could extract the transient free energy surface of the excited CDW state. Remarkably, our analysis revealed a transiently enhanced critical temperature T_c^* , which leads to CDW recovery for electronic temperatures far greater than the equilibrium T_c . We attributed this transient stabilization of CDW order to a suppression of fluctuations in the non-thermal lattice system initially after excitation [MWN21]. In addition, we studied the CDW-dependent relaxation dynamics of highly excited electrons far above E_F . Here, we found a remarkable modulation of the relaxation dynamics with the transient CDW gap size. Employing a time-dependent Green's function method (M. Sentef and M. Schüler), we could show that these oscillations originate from modulations of the electron-electron (e-e) scattering rates due to the CDW-modulated phase space for electron-hole pair excitations on the gapped part of the Fermi surface [MSW21].

Based on the gained understanding of CDW energy surfaces and scattering processes, we aimed at optically controlling CDW properties. These experiments were conducted on the transition-metal dichalcogenide (TMD) $1T\text{-TaS}_2$, which is discussed to host a combination of a CDW and a Mott state. In particular, a recently discovered meta-stable hidden (H) state has been identified in TaS_2 [9]. Using trARPES with two pump pulses, we demonstrated coherent control of the switching probability into this H-state by the order parameter amplitude mode, and identified the transition pathway into the H-state [MSD23].

Additional experiments employ the momentum microscope to investigate the momentum- and energy dependence of coherent phonon oscillations [5,8]. This ongoing work aims at extracting momentum-dependent e-ph coupling information throughout the whole Brillouin zone (BZ) and quantifying e-ph coupling matrix elements on the level of individual bands, and, e.g., their relevance for CDW order. Based on the momentum microscope, which yields time-resolved data

within the full BZ, we employ our recently developed multidimensional trARPES methodologies based on a Fourier domain analysis. A pixel-wise Fourier transform of TbTe₃ data, as shown in Fig. 2a demonstrates strongly momentum- and energy-dependent susceptibility to the CDW amplitude mode.

A more quantitative analysis employs a method for extracting quantitative e-ph matrix elements based on the imaginary part of the Fourier transformation of trARPES data [10]. In particular, the momentum-dependent e-ph matrix elements are derived by fitting the imaginary part of the Fourier transform with the derivative of the energy distribution curves (EDCs), shown for the case of TaS₂ in Fig. 2b. Results of this procedure are shown along Γ -M in Fig. 2c, demonstrating strongly momentum-dependent coupling of the amplitude mode to various energy bands within the analyzed region (manuscript in preparation).

Figure 2: Fourier ARPES Analysis. a) Momentum- and energy-dependent Fourier amplitude in TbTe₃. Bright color marks regions in momentum space susceptible to the CDW amplitude mode. b) Gamma-point EDC in TaS₂ (black), its derivative (blue), and the imaginary part of the Fourier transform (green). A fit of the scaled EDC derivative, yielding the e-ph coupling strength, is shown as dashed line. c) Energy-momentum dispersion along the Γ -M direction. Colored markers encode band position and relative e-ph coupling strength. Unpublished data.

Our studies in this subproject shed important light onto the mechanisms of CDW order, the dominating factors for CDW stabilization and the kinetics of ultrafast phase transitions. As prototypical examples, our results are also relevant for photoinduced phase transition in general. Furthermore, the quantification of fundamental interactions provides a microscopic picture of the interplay of the various degrees of freedom involved. Finally, ultrafast optical control of material parameters holds huge promises for future applications.

Antiferromagnetic systems

In the focus of the second subproject are interactions of the electronic and the spin subsystem, and in particular antiferromagnetic systems. Work on this project was performed by a PhD student (Sang-Eun Lee) and supported by a postdoc (Yoav William Windsor). Here, we predominantly focused on rare-earth intermetallics of type LnT_2Si_2 , with Ln a lanthanide and T a transition metal (Co, Rh, Ir), using both time-resolved resonant soft X-ray diffraction (trRXRD),

and trARPES. These compounds share a common layered crystal structure and magnetic motif of in-plane ferromagnetic and out-of-plane AFM order of $Ln 4f$ states, driven by indirect Rudermann-Kittel-Kasuya-Yosida (RKKY) exchange coupling [11]. Thus, these systems are particularly suited for a systematic study of the relation of exchange coupling and ultrafast magnetization dynamics.

In a large, systematic comparison of the magnetization dynamics in various members of the $LnRh_2Si_2$ series, we discovered a universality of the ultrafast demagnetization behavior, despite very large differences in absolute timescales. Remarkably, the extracted angular momentum (AM) transfer rates are found to scale with the de-Gennes factor, a measure of the strength of the RKKY exchange coupling. Based on *ab-initio* calculations of the AFM exchange parameter J_3 (V. Borisov, D. Thonig, O. Eriksson, A. Ernst), we found a direct relation of the AM transfer rates and the strength of RKKY coupling [WLZ22].

While this systematic study, by varying the Ln ion, predominantly investigated the role of the *on-site* $4f-5d$ coupling in the RKKY interaction, additional experiments were performed for $GdTSi_2$, with $T=Co, Rh, Ir$. By substitution of the T -ions, and their varying d -shell occupation, the influence of the coupling between neighboring Ln sites through the conduction electron channel could be studied. Our trRXRD studies, combined with orbital-resolved *ab-initio* calculations of the magnetic susceptibility (A. Ernst), uncovered two competing contributions to the RKKY interaction and the AM transfer in the system with opposite trend [LWZ24].

In order to more closely investigate the coupling of electronic and spin degrees of freedom in these systems, we also performed trARPES measurements in $GdRh_2Si_2$. Based on the exchange splitting of a surface state and the electronic temperature dynamics from trARPES, and the AFM order dynamics from trRXRD, we obtained a detailed picture of the coupling of bulk and surface magnetism, and of localized $4f$ and delocalized conduction band states. By applying a Landau-Lifshitz-Bloch model (U. Atxitia), we developed a unified description of energy transfer and bulk and surface magnetism [LWF22].

Due to its vanishing orbital moment, $GdRh_2Si_2$ has an isotropic $4f$ shell and a very weak magnetic anisotropy energy (MAE), making this system susceptible for optical control of magnetic order. By utilizing the anisotropy of magnetic scattering, we found that optical excitation can be used to control the AFM spin arrangement by transiently modifying the in-plane MAE potential, leading to a coherent magnon response of the whole spin structure. This not only provides quantitative information on the transient anisotropy potential, but also establishes a new transient control pathway for AFM spin arrangements [WEK20].

In a recent follow-up experiment driven by the PhD student Abeer Arora, we additionally employed a magnetic field to shape the anisotropy potential, providing a complementary control

knob. The magnetic field acts as a Zeeman torque on the AFM spin structure, and eventually leads to a spin-flop transition, where the AFM order rotates in-plane by 90° and slightly cants, leading to a drastic change of diffraction intensity (Fig. 3a). Upon ultrafast excitation, we observe similar to our previous experiment a coherent response of the AFM spin alignment, which shows a strong dependence on magnetic field (Fig. 3b). Most remarkably, for large enough B-fields we observe a sign reversal of the oscillations. The coherent response of the system can be modeled by the interplay of MAE and Zeeman energy, resulting in a global magnetic energy landscape (Fig. 3c). Using this approach, we could model the transient magnetic order dynamics including the sign reversal in the oscillations, and quantify the relevant energy scales dominating magnetic order in this material (Fig. 3d, manuscript in preparation).

Figure 3: Magnetic-field dependent optical control of spin order in GdRh_2Si_2 . a) magnetic field-dependent diffraction amplitude for horizontally (blue) and vertically (orange) aligned fields. b) Transient in-plane spin orientation as function of pump-probe delay for various magnetic fields. c) Schematic of the interplay of anisotropy and Zeeman energy, resulting in a spin-flop transition. Unpublished data. d) Modelled transient spin orientation. Insets schematically show the transient energy surfaces before (dashed) and after (solid) excitation. Unpublished data.

Complex transition metal oxides

The third subproject is focused on investigations of complex transition metal oxides with multiple coupled degrees of freedom. An important work focusing on the interplay of electronic and lattice degrees of freedom in charge- and orbitally ordered $\text{Pr}_{0.5}\text{Ca}_{0.5}\text{MnO}_3$ has been performed in collaboration with researchers from the Paul Scherrer Institute. Employing time-resolved hard X-ray diffraction on- and off-resonance with the Mn K -edge, we could show that coherent lattice modes predominantly modulate structural coordinates, and have little influence on the charge order parameter. This demonstrates that charge and orbital order is the primary instability, while lattice distortions play a secondary role in stabilizing the phase transition [RCM19]. Additionally, a study using ultrafast electron diffraction (UED) concentrated on the ultrafast lattice dynamics of the AFM Mott Insulator NiO. This work was performed using the UED setup

of the group of Ralph Ernstorfer on freestanding NiO films grown in Halle. Employing a novel approach for the analysis of Bragg-vector-dependent scattering amplitudes, we could unravel a long-lasting non-thermal lattice state after excitation in NiO. By further exploiting the sensitivity of UED to detect changes to the unit cell symmetry, we could attribute these changes to the release of exchange striction after photoexcitation in this strongly correlated magnetic oxide, a direct manifestation of spin-phonon coupling [WZK21].

A major line of research in this sub-project was dedicated to building a PLD setup for the growth of thin films and heterostructures of such materials, with the aim of performing trARPES experiments on such samples. After a commissioning phase, work had focused on charge-ordered

Figure 4: PLD-grown NdNiO₃ film characterization. a) LEED pattern of a 20 unit cell film of NdNiO₃ on NdGaO₃ substrate. b) Film resistivity hysteresis cycle. Unpublished data.

nickelates (NdNiO₃, LaNiO₃), as well as magnetic manganites and their heterostructures. While we succeeded with growth of such samples with good crystalline and electronic properties, as confirmed by x-ray diffraction, low-energy electron diffraction (LEED) and resistivity measurements (see Fig. 4), obtaining a surface quality suitable for ARPES measurements turned out to be a significant challenge. Work on this project is still ongoing.

Other projects

Beyond work along the main subprojects, several other research directions were also explored inside the scope of the Emmy-Noether project, mostly in collaboration with Ralph Ernstorfer's group.

In quasi 2-dimensional materials, electron-electron correlations can become particularly important, as screening effects are reduced due to the lowered dimension. This leads e.g. to extremely strong excitonic effects, such as in semiconducting TMDs. In WSe₂, we unraveled the properties of photoexcited excitons, including their binding energy, electron-phonon coupling parameters, and spatial distribution [12]. In addition, utilizing the full photoelectron spectrum accessible at the free-electron laser FLASH ranging from core levels to the valence and conduction bands [13], we found a strong dependence of the core-level spectral function on the nature of excited states in the material. Manifested by their stronger renormalization of the core-level spectral function, we could track the dissociation of initially excited excitons into quasi-free electron-hole pairs at the excitonic Mott transition, and thereby establish core-level photoemission spectroscopy as an element-specific probe of excited state dynamics, applicable also to various other materials [14].

Further work was dedicated to topological properties of the electronic system. A trARPES study of the TMD MoTe₂ revealed an ultrafast modulation of the Fermi surface topology, due to the transient shift of electron-like pockets below the Fermi level. By a combination with *ab-initio* calculations, we could identify a transient modification of the electronic correlations in the system as the origin of this ultrafast Lifshitz transition [15]. In addition, we investigated the transient electronic structure and scattering processes in the 2D quantum spin Hall insulator Bismuthene. In this study, we could not only identify for the first time the elusive dispersion of one-dimensional edge states, but also elucidate their decisive role for the surprisingly fast relaxation of excited carriers in this 2D topological insulator [MSD22].

Data handling and data management

All data relevant to publications obtained during this project are publicly available for download. In addition, in the context of the FAIRmat project of the NFDI, we are developing data and metadata schemas for various techniques ensuring open and F.A.I.R. data treatment.

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- [13] D. Kutnyakhov et al., *Time- And Momentum-Resolved Photoemission Studies Using Time-of-Flight Momentum Microscopy at a Free-Electron Laser*, Rev. Sci. Instrum. **91**, 013109 (2020).
- [14] M. Dendzik et al., *Observation of an Excitonic Mott Transition Through Ultrafast Core-Cum-Conduction Photoemission Spectroscopy*, Phys. Rev. Lett. **125**, 096401 (2020).
- [15] S. Beaulieu et al., *Ultrafast Dynamical Lifshitz Transition*, Sci. Adv. **7**, 9275 (2021).

4 Published Project Results

The publications listed here relate to the main findings of the project. A full list of publications of the project is attached.

4.1 Publications with scientific quality assurance

- [MSD23] J. Maklar, J. Sarkar, S. Dong, Y.A. Gerasimenko, T. Pincelli, S. Beaulieu, P.S. Kirchmann, J.A. Sobota, S.-L. Yang, D. Leuenberger, R.G. Moore, Z.-X. Shen, M. Wolf, D. Mihailovic, R. Ernstorfer, **L. Rettig**, *Coherent Light Control of a Metastable Hidden State*, *Science Advances* **9**, 47, adi4661 (2023)
- [LWF22] S.-E. Lee, Y. W. Windsor, A. Fedorov, K. Kliemt, C. Krellner, C. Schüßler-Langeheine, N. Pontius, M. Wolf, U. Atxitia, D. V. Vyalikh, **L. Rettig**, *Robust magnetic order upon ultrafast excitation of an antiferromagnet*, *Advanced Materials Interfaces* **9**, 2201340 (2022)
- [WLZ22] Y. W. Windsor, S.-E. Lee, D. Zahn, V. Borisov, D. Thonig, K. Kliemt, A. Ernst, C. Schüßler-Langeheine, N. Pontius, U. Staub, C. Krellner, D. V. Vyalikh, O. Eriksson, **L. Rettig**, *Exchange scaling of ultrafast angular momentum transfer in 4f antiferromagnets*, *Nature Materials* **21**, 514 (2022)
- [MSD22] J. Maklar, R. Stühler, M. Dendzik, T. Pincelli, S. Dong, S. Beaulieu, A. Neef, G. Li, M. Wolf, R. Ernstorfer, R. Claessen, **L. Rettig**, *Ultrafast Momentum-Resolved Hot Electron Dynamics in the Two-Dimensional Topological Insulator Bismuthene*, *Nano Letters* **22**, 5420 (2022)
- [MSW21] J. Maklar, M. Schüler, Y. W. Windsor, C. W. Nicholson, M. Puppin, P. Walmsley, I. R. Fisher, T. P. Devereaux, M. Wolf, R. Ernstorfer, M. A. Sentef, **L. Rettig**, *Coherent modulation of quasiparticle lifetimes in a photoexcited charge-density-wave system*, *Physical Review Letters* **128**, 026406 (2022)
- [WZK21] Y. W. Windsor, D. Zahn, R. Kamrla, J. Feldl, H. Seiler, C.-T. Chiang, M. Ramsteiner, W. Widdra, R. Ernstorfer, **L. Rettig**, *Exchange-striction driven ultrafast nonthermal lattice dynamics in NiO*, *Physical Review Letters* **126**, 147202 (2021)
- [MWN21] J. Maklar, Y. W. Windsor, C. W. Nicholson, M. Puppin, P. Walmsley, V. Esposito, M. Porer, J. Rittmann, D. Leuenberger, M. Kubli, M. Savoini, E. Abreu, S. L. Johnson, P. Beaud, G. Ingold, U. Staub, I. R. Fisher, R. Ernstorfer, M. Wolf, **L. Rettig**, *Nonequilibrium Charge-Density-Wave Order Beyond the Thermal Limit*, *Nature Communications* **12**, 2499 (2021)
- [MDB20] J. Maklar, S. Dong, S. Beaulieu, T. Pincelli, M. Dendzik, Y. W. Windsor, R. P. Xian, M. Wolf, R. Ernstorfer, **L. Rettig**, *A quantitative comparison of time-of-flight momentum microscopes and hemispherical analyzers for time-resolved ARPES experiments*, *Review of Scientific Instruments* **91**, 123112 (2020)
- [WEK20] Y. W. Windsor, A. Ernst, K. Kummer, K. Kliemt, Ch. Schüßler-Langeheine, N. Pontius, U. Staub, E. V. Chulkov, C. Krellner, D. V. Vyalikh, **L. Rettig**, *Deterministic control of an antiferromagnetic spin arrangement using ultrafast optical excitation*, *Communications Physics* **3**, 139 (2020)
- [RCM19] **L. Rettig**, A. Caviezel, S. O. Mariager, G. Ingold, C. Dornes, S.-W. Huang, J. A. Johnson, M. Radovic, T. Huber, T. Kubacka, A. Ferrer, H. T. Lemke, M. Chollet, D. Zhu, J. M. Glowina, M. Sikorski, A. Robert, M. Nakamura, M. Kawasaki, Y. Tokura, S. L. Johnson, P. Beaud, U. Staub, *Disentangling transient charge order from structural dynamics contributions during coherent atomic motion studied by ultrafast resonant x-ray diffraction*, *Phys. Rev. B* **99**, 134302 (2019)

4.2 Other publications and published results

- [LWZ24] S.-E. Lee, Y. W. Windsor, D. Zahn, A. Kraiker, K. Kummer, K. Kliemt, C. Krellner, C. Schüßler-Langeheine, N. Pontius, U. Staub, D. V. Vyalikh, A. Ernst, **L. Rettig**, *Controlling 4f antiferromagnetic dynamics via itinerant electronic susceptibility*, arXiv: 2404.12119 (2024)

4.3 Patents (applied for and granted)

None